

Analysis of Learning Readiness of Sports Teachers in Schools in Facing the New Normal Period of Covid-19

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ABSTRACT

All Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM) in Indonesia carry out the implementation of learning from home. The purpose of this study was to determine the readiness of sports teachers throughout the city of Bekasi in facing face-to-face learning during the new normal period due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Method : This type of research is a quantitative descriptive research. The population in this study were all junior high school sports teachers in the city of Bekasi. With the sampling technique of multistage random sampling, the sample in this study was 100 sports teachers. The data collection technique used survey instruments in the form of interviewers and interviews. Furthermore, the data analysis technique is in the form of descriptive analysis, namely by processing data and presenting data, calculating to describe the data, and testing hypotheses using statistical tests. It is hoped that it can become literature material for teachers to better prepare for face-to-face learning.

Keywords : readiness analysis; physical education; new normal

INTRODUCTION

Science and technology in sports learning has an important role in improving the quality of learning for students (Messakh et al., 2021). As it is today, society is highly dependent on technology. When the Covid-19 pandemic began at the end of December 2019, almost 90% of the entire population was using technology (Hanifah Salsabila et al., 2020). The emergency situation of the Covid-19 pandemic has an impact on the world of education. This is felt in almost all regions and at all levels of education from PAUD to tertiary institutions (Dewi, 2020).

Learning from home is a policy given by the government that is carried out by each education unit as a result of this impact. All Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM) in Indonesia carry out the implementation of learning from home (Ardonansyah et al., 2021). No exception in the subject of Physical Education

(PENJAS) (Aprilyadi et al., 2021). Sports teachers have a great responsibility to students to keep doing physical activity as a way to improve fitness and maintain immunity (Darmawan, 2018). Determining physical education learning media and methods need to be designed according to the conditions and abilities of students. This needs to be understood by educators to implement distance learning during a pandemic.

Seeing that the Covid-19 outbreak has shown a fairly stable decline, the government through the Minister of Education and Culture has issued a circular regarding face-to-face learning activities in the new normal period (Bangun et al., 2021). The new normal application pattern only applies if the area has a green zone status (Alaska & Hakim, 2021). The learning process carried out in the new normal is by doing blended learning, namely by combining online learning with

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face-to-face learning. However, various speculations emerged from the parents regarding the readiness of teachers and schools to carry out face-to-face learning. Many ask whether teachers are ready to run face-to-face learning, and whether they are ready to anticipate an increase in Covid-19 cases if the learning is carried out. Seeing these problems, sports teachers should be able to prepare the entire blended learning process so that it runs well and prepare various learning methods so that children do not feel burdened and bored.

Many analyzes related to teacher readiness in dealing with learning during the new normal have been carried out, including those that have been researched by (Waluyati et al., 2020) with their research entitled the application of the new normal during the Covid-19 pandemic in schools. Research conducted by (Shaleh & Anhusadar, 2021) which analyzed the readiness of PAUD institutions in face-to-face learning and (Alaska & Hakim, 2021) which analyzed the traditional sports such as ankle and jump rope in the new normal. Based on several studies that are considered relevant, the research results are still dominated by general research, there is no analytical research related to sports teachers.

In particular, this study aims to analyze the readiness of sports teachers in carrying out face-to-face learning during the new normal. This research will be carried out for 8 months with the output to be achieved in this research, namely the publication of articles in international journals, where the outputs of this research are in accordance with the directions and policies of the Bhayangkara University Research Strategic Plan, Greater Jakarta, namely developing the science of education and sports coaching in order to solve problems and

generate innovation at the local and national level.

Coronavirus-Disease 2019 or known as Covid-19 is one of the deadliest viruses throughout the world that has claimed many victims, including Indonesia (Handayani et al., 2020). According to (Susilo et al., 2020) this Covid-19 disease originated from Wuhan, China which entered Indonesia in early 2020. Along with the rapid development of gene mutations in this virus, Covid-19 also has variations ranging from delta to omicron variations. Covid-19 is said to be a deadly disease, especially for patients suffering from comorbid diseases. On the other hand, for patients who do not have a congenital disease (comorbid) Covid-19 can be cured by continuing to carry out strict health protocols (Angga & Kardiyanto, 2021).

Along with the high number of positive cases and deaths from this virus, the government through the Minister of Health issued a decision to carry out all activities at home (WFH) for all sectors, including education. The Minister of Education and Culture has issued a circular letter to carry out school activities from home, so that face-to-face activities at school are abolished (Priono, 2021). All schools were closed and replaced with distance learning (online). This situation lasted for almost a year until the Covid-19 death rate had decreased by the middle of 2021.

Currently, Indonesia is entering a new normal period, which means a period of life with a new order. Indonesia has resumed activities even though in the midst of the ongoing pandemic by continuing to carry out health protocols such as wearing masks, washing hands, and avoiding crowds (Darmawan &

Febrianti, 2021). In the new normal period, learning is set for students in Indonesia in the form of blended learning, namely face-to-face learning and e-learning. Provisions for carrying out new normal learning if the area that will carry out learning has the status of a green zone (Ridwan Ahmad Maftuhin & Danang Aji Setyawan, 2021).

The New Normal era that occurs in Indonesia affects the teaching and learning process in junior high schools, so that teaching and learning activities are carried out face-to-face in class and by online or distance learning (Fatimah, 2017). This of course has an impact on physical education learning at Junior High Schools in Bekasi including physical education learning that cannot be carried out in accordance with the lesson plans, teachers and students are not familiar with learning PJOK online because learning is usually done face-to-face, many students protest because too many tasks are given by the teacher, and parents have difficulty in assisting children to learn.

Not only in the learning process that cannot be implemented, but problems also occur in students. There are some students who experience problems in the online learning process. On the basis of these problems, the application of online learning does not always go well, there are many obstacles faced by teachers in carrying out learning and parents play a role in supervising children's learning processes at home, as well as technological developments that make students easily influenced by social media.

PJOK is an education where students can be fit and healthy. Students must reach the level of good or healthy

physically and mentally (Mendrofa, 2021). PJOK can make basic education in character building a generation. The objectives of PJOK learning are to lay down and develop (a) character foundations through internalization of values, (b) personality foundations (peace-loving, social, tolerance in ethnic and religious cultural pluralism, (c) critical thinking, (d) sportsmanship, honesty, discipline, responsible, cooperative, confident, and democratic, (e) movement skills, techniques, strategies for various games and sports, gymnastics, rhythmic activities, aquatics and education outside the classroom, (f) self-management skills, maintenance of physical fitness and lifestyle healthy, (g) skills to maintain the safety of oneself and others, (h) the concept of physical activity to achieve health, fitness and a healthy lifestyle, and (i) fill leisure time that is recreational (Mendrofa, 2021).

RESEARCH METHOD

This type of research is a quantitative research. The research method used is descriptive analysis. The population in this study were all junior high school (SMP) sports teachers in Bekasi City. Sampling in this study is by means of Multistage Random Sampling (taking in stages) so that 100 sports teachers were selected as samples in this study. The instruments used in this research are (1) survey instrument in the form of an opinion which is used to measure the readiness of sports teachers in implementing face-to-face learning; (2) interviews were used to further analyze the readiness for face-to-face learning. The data analysis techniques carried out are (1) quantitative analysis techniques by processing the results of survey

instruments; (2) qualitative analysis techniques by processing the results of teacher interviews.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To make it easier to explain the data, it will be divided by each factor that affects the process of implementing the categorization of online learning in the new normal period. The data that has been collected through questionnaires will then be described in order to

determine the readiness of sports teachers in junior high schools throughout the city of Bekasi in facing learning in the new normal period of Covid-19. The population in this study were all PJOK teachers in junior high schools throughout the city of Bekasi, totaling 30 people. The following is a table detailing the readiness of the Bekasi City Middle School PJOK teachers in facing learning in the new normal period of Covid-19.

Table 1
The Readiness of PJOK Teachers in Facing Learning in The New Normal Period of Covid-19

Overall	
N	30
Mean	109,09
Standart Deviation	47,0
Maximal	123
Minimum	86

Based on the data above, it can be seen that the sample is 30 PJOK teachers. For the Mean value of 109,09. Then the standard deviation is 4,70. The minimum

score is 86 and the maximum value is 123. Next, the score interval stage is carried out which can be seen in table 2 below.

Table 2
The PJOK Teacher Readiness Interval Score When Facing Learning in the New Normal Period of Covid-19

Interval Score	Criteria	Frekuensi	Percentage
$X \geq 116,14$	Very Ready	14	46,6%
$111,44 \leq X < 116,14$	Ready	6	20%
$106,74 \leq X < 111,44$	Quite Ready	5	16,6%
$102,04 < X < 106,74$	Not Ready	1	3,3%
$X \leq 102,04$	Very Upprepared	4	13,3%
Score		30	100%

Based on table 2 above, it can be seen the category of each teacher. For the very ready category as many as 14 people with

a percentage of 46,6%. For the ready category as many as 6 people with a percentage of 20%. For the quite ready

category, there are 5 people with a percentage of 16,6%. For the unprepared category as many as 1 person with a percentage of 3,3%. Then the last is the category of very unprepared as many as 4

people with a percentage of 13,3%. Furthermore, data scoring for each factor that affects PJOK teachers in dealing with online learning in the new normal can be seen in table 3 below :

Table 3
The Percentage of Total Score of Each Factor

Factor	Value	Percentage
Mental	901	26,64%
Physique	312	9,22%
Knowledge and Skills	2169	64,13%
Score	3382	100%

From table 3, it can be seen that the biggest factor that affects PJOK teachers is the knowledge and skills factor of 64,13%. then the mental factor is 26,64% and the smallest factor that influences is the physical factor is 9,22%. These data indicate that the knowledge and skills factor is the most important factor for PJOK teachers to be ready to face learning in the new normal period as a teacher.

Mental Factors for the Readiness of PJOK teachers to face learning in the new normal period of Covid-19

The results of the calculation of the data obtained for mental factors in the readiness of PJOK teachers in online learning with a total of 30 respondents are as follows.

Tabel 4
Description Mental Factor

Factor of Mental Data	
N	30
Mean	30,03
Standart Deviation	1,58
Minimum	27
Maximal	32

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the results of mental factors with a sample of 30 respondents had an average value (Mean) of 30,03. Then the

standard deviation of 1,58. Then the minimum value is 27 and the maximum value is 32.

Table 5
Mental Factors of Junior High School Teacher Readiness

Interval Score	Criteria	Frequency	Percentage
$X \geq 32,4$	Very ready	0	0%
$30,82 \leq X < 32,4$	Ready	13	43,3%
$29,24 \leq X < 30,82$	Quite Ready	4	13,3%
$27,66 \leq X < 29,24$	Not Ready	12	40%
$X \leq 27,66$	Not Prepared	1	3,3%
Total		30	100%

Based on the explanation from table 4 and figure 3 above, mental factors in influencing readiness are divided into 5 categories. The first is for the very ready category, namely 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% meaning that there are no respondents who are very ready in this mental factor. For the ready category there are 13 people with a percentage of 43,3%. For the fairly ready category, there are 4 people with a percentage of 13,3%. For the unprepared category there are 12 people with a percentage of 40%.

Then the last one is the very unprepared category, there is 1 person with a percentage of 3,3%.

Physical Factors for the Readiness of PJOK Teachers in Facing Online Learning in Junior High Schools

The results of the calculation of the data obtained by physical factors in the readiness of PJOK teachers in online learning with a total of 30 respondents are as follows :

Table 6
Description of Physical Factors

Data Physical Factors	
N	30
Mean	10,4
Standart Deviation	1,73
Minimum	6
Maximum	12

Based on the table above, it can be seen the results of physical factors with a sample of 30 respondents, namely the first is the average value (Mean) of 10,4.

Then the standard deviation of 1,77. Then the minimum value is 6 and the maximum value is 12. Then the calculation will continue in the interval table as follows :

Table 7
Physical Factors of Junior High School Teacher Readiness

Interval Score	Criteria	Frequency	Percentage
$X \geq 13,05$	Very Ready	0	0%
$11,28 \leq X < 13,05$	Ready	11	36,6%
$9,51 \leq X < 11,28$	Quite Ready	11	36,6%
$7,74 \leq X < 9,51$	Not Ready	5	16,6%
$X \leq 7,74$	Not Prepared	3	10%
Total		30	100%

Based on the explanation from the table, physical factors in influencing readiness are divided into 5 categories. The first for the very ready category is 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% meaning that there are no respondents who are very ready in this physical factor. For the ready category there are 11 people with a percentage of 36,6%. For the quite ready category, there are 11 people with a percentage of 36,6%. For the unprepared category there are 5 people with a percentage of 16,6%. Then the last one is

the very unprepared category, there are 3 people with a percentage of 10%.

Knowledge and Skills Factors for the Readiness of PJOK Teachers in Facing Online Learning in Junior High Schools

The results of the calculation of the data obtained by physical factors in the readiness of PJOK teachers in online learning with a total of 30 respondents are as follows :

Table 8
Description of Knowledge and Skill Factors

Description of Knowledge and Skill Factors	
N	30
Mean	72,3
Standart Deviation	4,28
Minimum	52
Maximal	80

Based on the table above, it can be seen the results of the knowledge and skills factor with a sample of 30 respondents, namely the first is the average value (Mean) of 72,3. Then the

standard deviation of 4,28. Then the minimum value is 52 and the maximum value is 80. Then the calculation will continue in the interval table as follows :

Table 9
Factors of Knowledge and Skills of Junior High School Teacher Readiness

Interval Score	Criteria	Frequency	Percentage
$X \geq 78,34$	Very Ready	7	23,3%
$74,31 \leq X < 78,34$	Ready	9	30%
$70,28 \leq X < 74,31$	Wuite Ready	6	20%
$66,25 \leq X < 70,28$	Not Ready	4	13,3%
$X \leq 66,25$	Not Prepared	4	13,3%
Total		30	100%

Based on the explanation from the table, physical factors in influencing readiness are divided into 5 categories. The first for the very ready category is 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% meaning that there are no respondents who are very ready in this physical factor. For the ready category there are 11 people with a percentage of 36,6%. For the fairly ready category, there are 13 people with a percentage of 43,3%. For the unprepared category there are 3 people with a percentage of 10%. Then the last one is the very unprepared category, there are 3 people with a percentage of 10%.

Teacher readiness in learning is one form of teacher professionalism. Preparation in the distance learning model is a competency that is not possessed by all teachers. The application of online learning requires careful preparation and planning from all parties involved starting from the school, teachers and students so that learning objectives can be achieved. In addition, according to (Mustofa et al., 2019) online learning is a distance learning system through several teaching methods, but teaching activities are carried out separately from learning activities. Meanwhile, according to (Ardian et al., 2019) explaining online learning is a

learning process whose interactions are connected by the internet.

Physical education is one of the efforts to create an environment that can affect the ability of students to develop towards positive behavior through physical activity. Therefore, PJOK teachers with their professional roles become important elements among other important elements in creating and developing learning activities and processes inside or outside the classroom (Rochman, 2016).

With the Covid-19 pandemic, learning has turned online. PJOK teachers in Bekasi City Junior High Schools must have mature readiness in carrying out online learning because according to Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers it is stated that teachers are professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing, and evaluate students in early childhood education through formal education, basic education, and secondary education.

The level of readiness of junior high school teachers in Bekasi City can be seen from various factors including mental factors, physical factors and knowledge and skills factors. For mental factors, such as an understanding of himself, the ability to think critically and develop the

potential that exists within him. For physical factors, such as physical conditions. For factors of knowledge and skills, such as providing online learning media and providing online assessments.

Based on the results of this study, which was conducted by distributing questionnaires with 31 questions that had passed the validity and reliability test. These questions have been filled out by 30 PJOK teachers at Bekasi City Junior High Schools who carry out online learning. The results of the study vary according to the opinion of each PJOK teacher. In this study, the purpose of this study was to determine the level of readiness of PJOK teachers at Bekasi City Junior High Schools in carrying out online learning in this new normal. Based on the results of the study, it was found that the level of readiness of PJOK teachers in Bekasi City who entered the very ready category was 14 people with a percentage of 46,6%, in the ready category as many as 6 people with a percentage of 20%, in the ready category as many as 5 people with a percentage of 16,6%, the unprepared category is 1 person with a percentage of 3,3%, and the very unprepared category is 4 people with a percentage of 13,3%. There are several factors of readiness that researchers can relate to this research, including mental readiness, meaning that the mental readiness of a teacher must be good and be able to adapt quickly to the Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia, such as implementing health protocols. in the school environment, then learning readiness means that before carrying out online learning the teacher must also study the material to be conveyed and make the right learning media for the learning so that the learning process can

run well. Then there is the physical factor, meaning that the teacher's physical is also required to always be excellent considering that online learning also makes the body tired if you are constantly in front of a computer, laptop or cellphone. Then there is the knowledge and skill factor, meaning that the teacher as much as possible must make online learning as fun as in class so that students are also interested in following it.

Based on the results of the research on mental factors in the readiness of PJOK teachers, there are no very ready categories at all, 13 people in the ready category with a percentage of 43,3%, a fairly ready category with 4 people with a percentage of 13,3%, a less ready category as many as 12 people with a percentage 40%, and the very unprepared category is 1 person with a percentage of 3,3%.

Based on the results of the research on physical factors in the readiness of PJOK teachers, there are no very ready categories at all, 11 people in the ready category with a percentage of 36,6%, a fairly ready category with 11 people with a 36,6% percentage, 5 people in the less ready category with a percentage of 36,6%. Percentage of 16,6%, and the category of very unprepared as many as 3 people with a percentage of 10%.

Based on the results of the research, the knowledge and skills factors in the readiness of PJOK teachers are very ready category as many as 7 people with a percentage of 23,3%, ready category as many as 9 people with a percentage of 30%, quite ready category as many as 6 people with a percentage of 20%, less ready category as many as 4 people with a percentage of 13,3%, and the very

unprepared category as many as 4 people with a percentage of 13,3%.

From several direct interviews that the researcher asked the school directly, it was for junior high school in Bekasi City that most of them carried out learning activities with Google Meet. Then in addition to learning PJOK the teachers gave a lot of videos of sports movements to the students then the students did the assignments given by the video instructions. For teachers who are technologically savvy, the school conducts training well until the teacher understands and can then apply it to teaching. In addition, facilities are also added, such as increasing the number of computers that are more sophisticated and repairing slow or damaged computers as well as adding an internet network so that the internet speed is also faster and learning activities are not disturbed by signals. For media for collecting assignments and giving assignments, teachers use Google Classroom and Whatsapp groups. When in school all teachers are also required to implement strict health protocols. In carrying out online learning during the pandemic, it is in the "very ready" category with a large percentage of 46,6%. This number is very far from the number of other categories and it is very encouraging because PJOK teachers are very ready to carry out online learning even though there are indeed some teachers who are also not ready, but the number of readiness is very high. Based on the results of this study, it can be seen that for the level of readiness of teachers of PJOK junior high school in Bekasi City.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the study, it was found that the level of readiness of PJOK teachers in the city of Bekasi for the very ready category was 14 people with a percentage of 46,6%, the ready category was 6 people with a percentage of 20%, the category was quite ready as many as 5 people with a percentage of 16,6%, the unprepared category is 1 person with a percentage of 3,3%, and the very unprepared category is 4 people with a percentage of 13,3%.

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